

The 3D Morphology of the Outer-Hair-Cell Hair Bundle Causes Spatial Variation in Its Stereocilium Displacements and Channel Currents

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Abstract. Outer-hair-cell hair bundles (OHBs) convert sound-induced forces into receptor currents, which drive cochlear amplification. OHBs comprise columns and V-shaped rows of filamentous stereocilia, pivoting at their insertion points in the hair-cell apex. Stereocilium deflections cause mechano-electrical-transduction (MET) channel gating, generating the receptor current. We use published data and our measurements of the stereocilium insertion points to build a 3D mathematical model of the OHB. The mathematical model enables us to calculate the resting orientations of the stereocilia. We find that stereocilium columns are far from parallel. To determine how the 3D morphology of the OHB affects the receptor current, we also calculate the receptor current for an OHB with identical columns (i.e., with parallel columns and lacking a V shape) for comparison. Owing to the 3D OHB's far-from-parallel columns and V shapes of the rows, stereocilium deflections vary much more in the 3D OHB than in the identical-columns OHB. Stereocilium-deflection variation causes variation in the currents passing through the MET channels. Variation in stereocilium deflections and MET channel currents are associated with, respectively, a 200% increase in the 3D OHB's mean deflection and in its receptor-current dynamic range in comparison with the identical-columns OHB.

INTRODUCTION

Outer-hair-cell hair bundles (OHBs) are required for the high sensitivity, sharp frequency tuning, and large dynamic range of hearing [1]. An OHB comprises actin-packed stereocilia inserted in the outer-hair-cell apex (Fig. 1A) [2]. Stereocilia are arranged in columns and rows. In a column, stereocilia of increasing height are linked by gating springs that gate mechano-electrical-transduction (MET) channels. Rows are defined by stereocilia of similar height and are V shaped. Sound-induced stimulus forces on the tallest row of stereocilia (row 1) deflect the OHB stereocilia, modulating the gating-spring forces that open and close the MET channels in the shorter rows (rows 2 and 3). The opening and closing of the MET channels cause oscillating MET-channel currents, which sum to produce the oscillating receptor current.

Prior work suggests that the OHB's V shape decreases the drag associated with fluid flow around the OHB [3]. Here, we focus on how the OHB's shape affects its stereocilium deflections and MET currents in response to a sinusoidal force stimulus. We use a 3D mathematical model of the OHB to calculate its responses to stimulation.

RESULTS

We construct the 3D-OHB model for the 4-kHz characteristic-frequency location in postnatal-day 7–16 (P7–16) rats. Because all the parameters needed are not available for one characteristic-frequency location, in one species, and at one age, we use data from the most developed ages possible and some parameters from measurements in mice and guinea pigs. The stereocilium heights, widths, and resting gating-spring lengths are based on electron and light microscopy data (Fig. 1A) [4, 5, 6].

Using optical microscopy, we measure the stereocilium pivot positions in the hair-cell apex in a P10 rat (Fig. 1B). We find that the columns of pivot points, which correspond to stereocilia linked by gating springs, are far from parallel (up to 67° between columns). Each row has a curved V shape. To determine how the far-from-parallel columns and V shape affect the 3D OHB's responses, we compare it to an identical-columns OHB (Fig. 1C). The identical-columns OHB is the same as the 3D OHB except that its pivot-position columns are parallel to the X-axis, its pivot-position rows are parallel to the Y-axis (i.e., it is not V shaped), and its stereocilium columns are independent. Additionally, in the identical-columns OHB, pivot spacings within columns equal the mean spacing within columns of the 3D OHB.

FIGURE 1. The effects of an OHB's 3D morphology are assessed using 3D and identical-columns OHB models. (A) The morphology of the 3D-OHB model is shown. Stereocilia of different rows have different heights. Stereocilia are linked by connectors (red, cyan) and gating springs (green) that gate MET channels (brown dots), through which the receptor current flows. In response to a sound-induced stimulus force (double-headed arrow) applied to the tallest row (row 1, blue), stereocilia deflect around their pivots (blue dots) in the hair-cell apex (gray box). (B) To illustrate the linking pattern, pivot points (dots) in the hair-cell apex (gray) are joined by lines representing the connectors and gating-springs. The stimulus is approximately parallel to the notch column (black dashed box). (C) The linking pattern and pivot positions of the identical-columns OHB are shown. Because columns are identical, identical-column results are calculated using a single column and there are no connectors within rows.

Unlike the morphological parameters of the OHB model, the mechanical parameters are not directly measured in experiments but can be inferred by fitting experimental observations. We find the stiffnesses, unloaded states, and damping coefficients of the stereocilia, connectors, and gating springs by fitting the 3D-OHB model to nine independent experimental measurements [5, 6, 7, 8]. The timescale for MET-channel opening and fluid-coupling damping coefficients are based on prior work [9, 10, 11]. We describe connectors using viscoelastic elements and a repulsive force between neighboring stereocilia caused by the glycocalyx, which prevents stereocilium membranes from coming into contact [12, 13].

In contrast to bundles in frogs and turtles, we lack direct evidence of mechanical activity in OHBs [2, 14]. Accordingly, the model OHB is mechanically passive. Likewise, because the mechanisms responsible for receptor-current adaptation are under debate, we do not include adaptation in the model OHB [2, 15]. This approach emphasizes that mechanical activity and adaptation are not required for the effects we describe.

Solving the nonlinear force-balance equations between stereocilium pivots and links at rest, reveals that the stereocilia lean far from the vertical at rest (Fig. 1A). In particular, row 1 stereocilia lean toward the notch column and toward row 3 by 693–1134 nm. Because of this leaning, stereocilia move in the X and Y directions in response to a stimulus force in the X direction. Row 1 leaning toward row 3 agrees with prior electron-microscopy measurements [16].

Because we use the measured response to a 40-Hz sinusoidal fluid-jet to calibrate our 3D model, we apply a similar stimulus in our models [8]. In response a sinusoidal force on the row-1 tips, the stereocilia in each row deflect with very different amplitudes in the X and Y directions (Fig. 2A–F). Amplitude variation is much larger in Y than in X. Owing to nonlinearities caused by OHB morphology, some stereocilia oscillate asymmetrically around their resting deflections, their oscillations are periodic but not sinusoidal, and/or they oscillate at twice the stimulus frequency. In contrast to the deflections, there is little variation in the zero crossings. Stereocilia on the left and right of the notch column move in antiphase in the Y direction, similar to prior experimental observations (Fig. 2D–F) [17].

FIGURE 2. Stereocilium deflections and channel currents vary substantially across the 3D OHB. (A–F) X- and Y-deflections relative to stereocilium resting deflections are shown versus time in response to a 40-Hz force (15 pN per row 1 stereocilium) for the 3D OHB. (G,H) Channel currents are shown versus time. (I) The mean row 2, mean row 3, and receptor current (brown) are shown versus time. Colors are lighter for stereocilia further from the notch column and correspond to row 1 (blue), row 2 (purple), and row 3 (orange) (Fig. 1B).

We calculate the normalized current (open probability) of each MET channel versus time. There is considerable variation in MET current amplitudes within and between rows (Fig. 2G,H). Row-2 current amplitudes vary more than those of row 3. Some MET channels open and close almost completely (MET current curves flatten near the values of 0 and 1), whereas other MET channels open and close much less. Because stereocilium deflections drive MET-channel gating, a few MET-channel currents oscillate asymmetrically around their resting currents, their oscillations are periodic but not sinusoidal, and/or they oscillate at twice the stimulus frequency. Like the stereocilium deflections, there is little variation in the zero crossings. The mean row-2 current is smaller than the mean row-3 current (Fig. 2I). The sum of the MET currents yields the receptor current, which is normalized to the maximum current for the whole OHB (Fig. 2I).

By construction in the identical-columns OHB, there is no variation in stereocilium deflections or current within each row and Y deflections are zero (Fig. 3A). The 3D OHB X-deflection amplitudes of row 1 are twice as large as those in the identical-columns OHB (Figs. 2A and 3A). Like the 3D OHB, there is little zero-crossing variation between rows in the identical-columns OHB (Figs. 2A–C and 3A).

In the identical-columns OHB, there is very little variation in the row 2 and row 3 currents, which are almost identical to the normalized receptor current (Fig. 3B). The 3D OHB's mean row 2, mean row 3, and receptor current are all smaller than those of the identical-columns OHB (Figs. 2I and 3B).

To determine how the receptor current is related to the mean row-1 X deflection, we apply a large amplitude 40-Hz sinusoidal force and calculate the receptor-current as a function of the deflection (Fig. 3C). Like prior experiments, there is little hysteresis and the 0.1–0.9 dynamic range from plateau-to-plateau is 76 nm in the 3D OHB [8]. The 3D OHB's dynamic range is twice that of the identical-columns OHB (31 nm). Unlike the identical-columns OHB, the 3D OHB's receptor current does not asymptote to zero for large negative deflections. This small deviation from zero has likely been interpreted to be a non-MET current in prior experiments and been subtracted from the measured current [8, 15].

FIGURE 3. Deflection variation, current variation, and the dynamic range of the 3D OHB are substantially larger than those of the identical-columns OHB. (A) X deflections relative to stereocilium resting deflections are shown versus time in response to a 40-Hz force (15 pN per row 1 stereocilium) for the identical-columns OHB. (B) The mean row 2, mean row 3, and receptor current (brown) are shown versus time for the identical-columns OHB. (A,B) Colors correspond to row 1 (blue), row 2 (purple), and row 3 (orange) (Fig. 1B). (B) The differently-colored lines almost completely overlap because the currents have almost identical time courses. (C) In response to one cycle of a 40-Hz sinusoidal stimulus force with a 980 pN amplitude, the normalized receptor current versus the mean row-1 X displacement is shown for the 3D OHB (brown) and the identical-columns OHB (light brown). The 0.1–0.9 dynamic ranges are delimited by dots (0.1–0.9 of the plateau-to-plateau range).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We show that an OHB's far-from-parallel columns and V shape have large effects on its stereocilium deflections and MET currents. In comparison the identical-columns OHB, the 3D OHB has much more variable deflections and MET-currents, half the stiffness (row-1 deflections are halved), and double the dynamic range.

An OHB's far-from-parallel columns is a different feature from its V shape. The far-from-parallel columns causes stereocilia to lean toward the notch column at rest, moving the orientation of the gating springs away from the X direction and creating Y deflections in response to X-direction stimuli. These changes in gating-spring orientation and Y deflections decrease the 3D OHB's stiffness and increase its dynamic range.

Measured OHB deflections and receptor currents are often used to infer the physiological properties of the OHB [6, 8, 18]. The model most commonly used to interpret these measurements is the identical-gating model, in which all stereocilium deflections in a given row are assumed to be the same and all MET currents are assumed to be identical [18]. Because we show that stereocilium deflections and MET currents are far from identical, we expect there to be large systematic errors in the physiological properties inferred from prior experiments.

Our work implies that developmental, mutational, and tonotopic changes in the pivot positions will change the OHB's stiffness and receptor-current dynamic range. Several mutations change the pivot positions in OHBs and cause hearing loss [19, 20, 21]. It is also possible that the tonotopic changes in the gating-spring and pivot effective stiffnesses calculated in prior work using an identical-gating model are caused by tonotopic changes in the pivot positions [6]. Pivot-position differences likely cause large functional differences between OHB's, inner-hair-cell bundles, vestibular bundles, non-mammalian hearing bundles, and lateral-line bundles [2].

There may be no evidence for mechanical activity in OHBs because the *in vivo* conditions required for activity have not yet been reproduced in *ex vivo* preparations [2, 14]. Like the passive OHB presented here, we expect the 3D morphology of an active OHB to reduce its stiffness. Active OHB motility has been mathematically modeled in 3D and identical-gating OHBs [18, 22, 23, 24, 25]. In these models, the interplay of adaptation processes and the nonlinearity of MET channel gating can produce a spontaneously oscillating OHB that can amplify stimulus forces in a frequency-dependent manner [18, 22]. We show that an OHB's 3D structure broadens the receptor-current nonlinearity, which is expected to change the conditions for spontaneous oscillations [22].

We have chosen to omit adaptation in the OHB models presented here because there is considerable uncertainty surrounding the mechanisms causing OHB adaptation [2, 15]. The OHB parameters we fit to experimental observations are effective parameters that contain the effects of adaptation. Like the results presented here, we expect the 3D OHB morphology to increase the receptor-current dynamic range in the presence of adaptation. Because our results show that the OHB's 3D morphology has a large effect on the receptor current, we also expect the OHB's 3D morphology to affect receptor-current adaptation.

The dynamic range of hearing relies on cochlear nonlinearity which is based for the most part on the dynamic range of the OHB receptor current [18, 23, 25, 26]. Accordingly, the OHB's 3D morphology doubling its dynamic range is expected to have a big effect on the dynamic range of hearing.

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REFERENCES

1. A. J. Hudspeth, “Making an effort to listen: Mechanical amplification in the ear,” *Neuron* **59**, 530–545 (2008).
2. D. Ó Maoiléidigh and A. J. Ricci, “A bundle of mechanisms: Inner-ear hair-cell mechanotransduction,” *Trends Neurosci* **42**, 221–236 (2019).
3. N. Ciganović, A. Wolde-Kidan, and T. Reichenbach, “Hair bundles of cochlear outer hair cells are shaped to minimize their fluid-dynamic resistance,” *Scientific Reports* **7**, 3609 (2017).
4. D. N. Furness, S. Mahendrasingam, M. Ohashi, R. Fettiplace, and C. M. Hackney, “The dimensions and composition of stereociliary rootlets in mammalian cochlear hair cells: comparison between high- and low-frequency cells and evidence for a connection to the lateral membrane,” *J Neurosci* **28**, 6342–6353 (2008).
5. D. N. Furness, Y. Katori, B. Nirmal Kumar, and C. M. Hackney, “The dimensions and structural attachments of tip links in mammalian cochlear hair cells and the effects of exposure to different levels of extracellular calcium,” *Neuroscience* **154**, 10–21 (2008).
6. M. Tobin, A. Chaiyasitdhi, V. Michel, N. Michalski, and P. Martin, “Stiffness and tension gradients of the hair cell’s tip-link complex in the mammalian cochlea,” *Elife* **8** (2019), 10.7554/eLife.43473.
7. A. X. Cartagena-Rivera, S. Le Gal, K. Richards, E. Verpy, and R. S. Chadwick, “Cochlear outer hair cell horizontal top connectors mediate mature stereocilia bundle mechanics,” *Sci Adv* **5**, eaat9934 (2019).
8. S. L. Johnson, M. Beurg, W. Marcotti, and R. Fettiplace, “Prestin-driven cochlear amplification is not limited by the outer hair cell membrane time constant,” *Neuron* **70**, 1143–1154 (2011).
9. M. Beurg, J.-H. Nam, and R. Fettiplace, “The speed of the hair cell mechanotransducer channel revealed by fluctuation analysis,” *J Gen Physiol* **153** (2021), 10.1085/jgp.202112959.
10. K. K. Miller, P. Atkinson, K. R. Mendoza, D. Ó Maoiléidigh, and N. Grillet, “Dimensions of a living cochlear hair bundle,” *Front Cell Dev Biol* **9**, 742529 (2021).
11. J. Baumgart, *The Hair Bundle: Fluid-Structure Interaction in the Inner Ear*, Ph.D. thesis, Technische Universität Dresden (2011).
12. A. C. LeBoeuf, D. Ó Maoiléidigh, and A. J. Hudspeth, “Divalent counterions tether membrane-bound carbohydrates to promote the cohesion of auditory hair bundles,” *Biophys J* **101**, 1316–1325 (2011).
13. W. L. Jongebloed, E. A. Dunnebier, F. W. Albers, and D. Kalicharan, “Demonstration of the fine structure of stereocilia in the organ of corti of the guinea pig by field emission scanning electron microscopy,” *Scanning Microsc* **10**, 147–163 (1996).
14. D. P. Corey, D. Ó Maoiléidigh, and J. F. Ashmore, “Mechanical transduction processes in the hair cell,” in *Understanding the Cochlea*, edited by G. A. Manley, A. W. Gummer, A. N. Popper, and R. R. Fay (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017) pp. 75–111.
15. G. A. Caprara and A. W. Peng, “Mechanotransduction in mammalian sensory hair cells,” *Mol Cell Neurosci* **120**, 103706 (2022).
16. D. N. Furness, D. E. Zetes, C. M. Hackney, and C. R. Steele, “Kinematic analysis of shear displacement as a means for operating mechanotransduction channels in the contact region between adjacent stereocilia of mammalian cochlear hair cells,” *Proc Biol Sci* **264**, 45–51 (1997).
17. A. W. Peng, A. L. Scharr, G. A. Caprara, D. Nettles, C. R. Steele, and A. J. Ricci, “Fluid jet stimulation of auditory hair bundles reveal spatial non-uniformities and two viscoelastic-like mechanisms,” *Front Cell Dev Biol* **9**, 725101 (2021).
18. D. Ó Maoiléidigh and A. J. Hudspeth, “Effects of cochlear loading on the motility of active outer hair cells,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **110**, 5474–5479 (2013).
19. A. Lelli, V. Michel, J. Boutet de Monvel, M. Cortese, M. Bosch-Grau, A. Aghaie, I. Perfettini, T. Dupont, P. Avan, A. El-Amraoui, and C. Petit, “Class iii myosins shape the auditory hair bundles by limiting microvilli and stereocilia growth,” *J Cell Biol* **212**, 231–244 (2016).
20. Y. Liu, J. Qi, X. Chen, M. Tang, C. Chu, W. Zhu, H. Li, C. Tian, G. Yang, C. Zhong, Y. Zhang, G. Ni, S. He, R. Chai, and G. Zhong, “Critical role of spectrin in hearing development and deafness,” *Sci Adv* **5**, eaav7803 (2019).
21. A. Akturk, M. Day, and B. Tarchini, “Rgs12 polarizes the gpsm2-gnai complex to organize and elongate stereocilia in sensory hair cells,” *Sci Adv* **8**, eabq2826 (2022).
22. J.-H. Nam and R. Fettiplace, “Theoretical conditions for high-frequency hair bundle oscillations in auditory hair cells,” *Biophys J* **95**, 4948–4962 (2008).
23. D. Ó Maoiléidigh and F. Jülicher, “The interplay between active hair bundle motility and electromotility in the cochlea,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **128**, 1175–1190 (2010).
24. J. Meaud and K. Grosh, “Coupling active hair bundle mechanics, fast adaptation, and somatic motility in a cochlear model,” *Biophys. J.* **100**, 2576–2585 (2011).
25. J.-H. Nam and R. Fettiplace, “Optimal electrical properties of outer hair cells ensure cochlear amplification,” *PLoS ONE* **7**, e50572 (2012).
26. J. Meaud and K. Grosh, “Response to a pure tone in a nonlinear mechanical-electrical-acoustical model of the cochlea,” *Biophys J* **102**, 1237–1246 (2012).

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Gabriel Alberts]: 60 nm deflection (Fig 2A) seems like a lot to me. Is it? If so, are the effects you're seeing only present for high level stimuli? What are the effects at low levels?

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: For the large but non-saturating stimulus used here, the mean displacement amplitude is about 50 nm, which is consistent with the measured 0.1–0.9 dynamic range of the OHB (75 nm) (Johnson et al. (2011) *Neuron*). Many of the effects we see are present for stimuli of all sizes. High-level and low-level effects are shown in an upcoming publication.

[Gabriel Alberts]: Fig 3C shows a current of 0.5 for 0 nm X deflection in both cases. Since the current is typically asymmetric, were these lines normalized about that point to show the dynamic range difference more clearly? Was the open probability in your models set to 0.5 for 0 nm deflection? Does the V shape or column "off-parallelness" affect the asymmetry?

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: The curves were not adjusted to show the dynamic range difference more clearly. Because the resting open probabilities of the 3D and identical-columns OHBs were chosen to be 0.5, the curves overlap at 0.5. The V shape has a small effect on the displacement-current curve, which is shown in an upcoming publication.

[Paul Secchia]: Hi Dáibhid, that was a really cool talk. I saw in your model and in some of the TEM images a left-right asymmetry in the pivot positions. I want to know if you have any thoughts on that matter.

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: Absolutely, so we had a few hair bundles available to look at and we picked the most symmetric one. It turns out, generally speaking, the bundles are not symmetric. There may be differences between the outer-hair-cell rows. This is something we want to work on further, but I think we need more data to be systematic. I could of course make it not symmetric and not surprisingly you're going to change the stimulus direction for which you get the maximum response. This bundle has maximum response when the stimulus is parallel to the central column. When you vary the stimulus direction you see a smaller response.

[Paul Secchia]: Follow-up question. In the asymmetry, is one side systematically more on the basal end versus the apical end?

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: We don't have enough data to answer that question at present. It could be the case.

[Martin Göpfert]: You showed us that there are more stereocilia in the beginning and are more abundant during development. Can you comment on those, why they are given up and what the advantage is of getting rid of these stereocilia?

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: It's not clear. You may think that it helps to gate channels more synchronously. However, we haven't found any evidence for that. We've looked at some models with additional rows for significant timing differences. So right now, I can't tell you. We have some preliminary data where we model bundles with many rows versus bundles with fewer rows, but we're not sure what the answer is yet.

[Chris Bergevin]: Nice talk. Roughness is a big theme at this conference. Can pivot position in any meaningful way contribute to roughness?

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: Sure. When people present the hair bundle they emphasize the beautiful paracrystalline array, it's perfect, but it's not perfect. It's not even exactly hexagonal. It's a pseudo-hexagonal pattern on the surface. We were looking for a clear hexagonal pattern on the surface of the cell, but we didn't find it. It's as if you took a hexagonal pattern and deformed it and stretched it out.

[Jong-Hoon Nam]: Nice talk. This is maybe the most dedicated effort to reflect bundle geometry, so my questions are relevant to bundle geometry. I have three subquestions. Your mention of mildly-fixed probably is a consideration. During fixation morphology changes. Could you talk a little about that? Second thing is development. You used P10 animal. Is the bundle fully developed at P10 or could it further develop later on? I forgot my third question.

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: So for the first question. We did some work where we looked at inner-hair-cell hair bundles. We looked at bundles that were mildly fixed and at bundles that were not fixed at all, but a dye was put into the membrane, which intercalated between the lipids and allowed use to image the unfixed geometry and morphology. We didn't see any difference between the unfixed preparation and the fixed preparation, with the exception of, in the fixed preparation we use fluorescence against the actin core, so the widths looked a little narrower, whereas in the unfixed preparation we were labeling the membrane, so the widths were a bit wider. For the second question, in

development, I would love to know what the developmental changes are. We going with the data we have available. All I can say right now, is I know in hamsters, by the time you get to P9, there no change in bundle height anymore. I know that in rats, the species we looked at, between P12 and P24 there is no change in height, but I don't know if there are changes between P10 and P12 in height. It does appear that the outer-hair-cell bundle gets to its mature morphology earlier than the inner-hair-cell hair bundle. But, we haven't looked at pivot positions and we haven't done a systematic study. So I would love to get that data, so we could check exactly what you're asking.

[Pascal Martin]: Could you clarify a bit the nature of the stimulus knowing that in vivo the tallest row is embedded into a tectorial membrane, which constrains the way it can move.

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh]: That's a good question. Some people think that the tectorial membrane is a displacement input to the hair bundle, which dictates how the stereocilia move. There's a conceptual problem with this idea, because the stereocilia are pivoting rods. If you constrain a stereocilium's displacement, using the tectorial membrane to prevent it from moving laterally, than you have to worry about the z-displacement, which you're also constraining. So either the stereocilia have to shrink, to accommodate the z-displacement, or their indentation into the tectorial membrane has to change, to accommodate the z-displacement. What these accommodations would do is to reduce the relationship between reticular-lamina and tectorial-membrane motion and hair-bundle motion. Instead of getting shearing motion, you'll get some bundle compression, which won't be optimal for opening the MET channels. You can choose that scenario, if you wish, but there will be a downside. So I think that the impedance of the tectorial membrane, although larger than that of the bundle, is not sufficiently large to completely dictate bundle displacement.